

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF THE LESSONS ON MUSIC CULTURE IN ELEMENTARY GRADES OF GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS

¹Abdivali Pardayev Sobit ugli, ²Murodova Munisa Shuhrat qizi

¹The "Music Education" department of Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical Institute

²2nd year student of the "Music Education" department of Uzbekistan-Finland Pedagogical
Institute

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Abstract. *In this article The specific features of primary school music culture lessons are revealed, and music equips a person with artistic aesthetic taste and shapes his spiritual world.*

Keywords: *general education schools, primary school, science, education, listening to music, happiness, entertainment, local performance.*

It's difficult to imagine human life without the art of music . The study and analysis of human society shows that music has been an integral part of a person's life during periods of good perception of the world. From the moment a person is born from the mother, without being ready to feel, understand and perceive the existence, he feels the mother's alla, a crying child stops crying, is soothed and rests.

Music has not only been a means of joy, happiness, and entertainment for people, but it has also been a companion in sad moments and performed the task of comfort and consolation.

Joy, fun, expression of joy, spiritual need, a unique kind of knowledge, educational tool, what else! Divine feeling!

Gradually, with the development of human society, the growth of social and cultural life, as a result of the development of science, attention to music, along with all other sciences, appeared, and it was viewed as a science. Aristotle, the world's first teacher, said that "music has the ability to influence the divine aspects of the soul. As long as this is the case, it should be included among the means of educating people.

With the development of science, education, music became taught as a science. In music, the words and the voice are in perfect harmony, and it teaches a person to perceive and appreciate the surrounding events in an artistically beautiful way. Arms a person with artistic aesthetic taste and shapes his spiritual world.

Music education and training that exists in our educational institutions today as a science, first of all, introduces the growing young generation to the simplest laws of music, notation, vocal-choir, theoretical rules, and it implies educating them in the basics of music culture.

The tasks for the implementation of this higher goal are as follows:

1. Forming and developing interest and love in students and young people for the art of music, first of all for our national music, for the national musical heritage of our people that has been passed down from generation to generation.

2. Deep feeling of music, appreciation of it, perception of unique theoretical and practical performance characteristics, harmony, similarities and differences of national and modern music.

3. Knowing, distinguishing, and expressing one's attitude to the popular genres of folk music, national instruments.
4. Having information about the local performance styles in the borders of Uzbekistan, to be aware of the concepts of classical and maqam music.
5. Distinguishing artistic works that are examples of high creativity and works of low level, to be able to evaluate them.
6. Sister nations and foreign music culture.
7. Having the ability to think and use in practical experience while understanding the ideological and artistic content of the works.
8. To achieve the development of creativity skills in the process of musical activities.
9. Through music, to awaken love and passion for Mother Nature, Mother Nature, people, life, and profession, and develop feelings of humanity.

Music culture lessons in primary grades of general education schools are special. Musical education in elementary grades is organized on the basis of several activities. **These are.**

1. Listen to music.
2. Singing in a group (choir).
3. Music literacy (giving theoretical knowledge).
4. Children's musical instruments.
5. Perform dance and rhythmic movements to music (musical creativity).

Among these activities, listening to music is the leading activity. It is very important for children to love the works they listen to in order to arouse their passion for music.

As person hears a good piece of music (song or tune) from a skilled performer, impressions and opinions about the piece of music arise. How listeners perceive a piece of music is influenced by how the music sounds and how well the musician or singer performs. That is why the professional skills of school music teachers in playing musical instruments are of great importance in music lessons. Music works of simple and complex genres are listened to in phonotheque, audio, video recordings through technical means. When performing such works, the music teacher's performance skills may be limited and he may not be able to give the students enough artistic and emotional pleasure.

A methodically skilled music leader (teacher) can organize children to listen to music in a highly emotional state by skillfully using various technical tools, audio images, computer and multimedia tools that are the subject of our research. They should be able to effectively use the available technical and visual tools in order to understand the true nature of new musical works and their meaning. However, it should be noted that it has been established in the experience that the work performed live leaves a greater impression on children.

The main tasks for listening to music in elementary grades; includes two main directions.

1. Acquaintance with works of different content and different authors, collecting musical reserve.
2. Understand various musical terms and concepts. Acquiring the expressive means of different music, basic understanding of the elements of a musical work. In the methodologically different interpretation of the lessons in the music education system, the musical content of the piece listened to during the training should come from the theme of the quarter (year) in terms of artistic and ideological theme.

It can be divided into the following stages

1. Introduction of the teacher about the works to be listened to (story, conversation).

2. Listening to musical works on musical instruments or using technical means.

3. Listened work through conversation, question-and-answer.

Making a final conclusion about the general impression of the students after re-listening to the musical work as a whole.

The activity of listening to music, students are formed the following skills and abilities;

- listen carefully to musical works;

understand its content and character when listening to a sar;

means of expression, genres of music (song, dance, waltz march, etc.);

- to be able to hear and distinguish the voices of men, women, children and mixed choirs, solo, chorus;

- distinguish between national instruments, ensembles, orchestra types, musical genres;

Music listening exercises are performed during all types of activities.

Singing activity

This type of activity is favorite, most popular and understandable for children. Almost all children love to sing. Singing a spoon has a strong emotional impact. Because the artistic unity of text and melody is invisible in the song. The song has an effective effect on the growth of mental maturity, the expansion of the worldview, and the enrichment of the imagination.

In the process of singing, students perceive music more deeply. The ideological -artistic content of the song (the idea expressed in the text) helps children to understand the content of music and learn it more easily. Children develop musical hearing ability, musical memory , sense of meter and rhythm, musical hearing and sense of rhythm during singing activities .

In the process of singing as a group, the student tries to control his own voice, listen to the performance of his friends while singing, and sing with them in an ensemble, as a result, collective unity, organization, self-esteem. a sense of belonging is cultivated.

Process of singing has a good effect on the development of children's speech (diction). Because the words of the song are played out, children learn the words without notes. Children's voice is soft and amplified through a sound resonator.

The resonator is divided into two.

1. High head resonator.

2. Lower chest resonator.

It should be said that the voice of young children is fragile and undeveloped. The time from the age of 7 to 13 is the time when the voice becomes low. By the age of 11-13, the larynx muscles are fully formed in children and continue to develop until the age of 20.

The voice of first graders sounds well in the range of mi-1 sol-1, fa-1 lya-1.

The voices of second-grade students sound more natural in the si-1 range.

In the third-fourth grades, the students' voice sounds fully in the do-1 re-2 (mi-2) range.

Fourth-grade students is in the range of do-1, mi-2 (fa -2). In order to properly educate the voice of children from primary grades, it is necessary to pay serious attention to the development of vocal and choral skills in them.

Vocal-choir qualifications are divided into the following types

1. Singing position (standing, sitting singing position).
2. Breathing.
3. Making a sound.
4. Word.
5. Pronunciation.
6. Ensemble.

Singing according to the note in the process of acquiring musical knowledge (solfeccio) is a complex process. Solfeccio is a vocal exercise for learning Italian notes, musical symbols, gammas for the development of singing-listening skills and learning to read them quickly depending on the note.

If students gradually improve their ability to sing according to the notes, from simple to complex, they can easily sing the songs they have learned according to the notes when they move to higher classes.

Before singing, the measure of the melody, the length of the notes involved, the tempo and tonality of the melody are determined. Then in this tonality, voice tuning exercises are performed, adaptation to the tonality (adjustment) is performed.

Music literacy. Music literacy classes mainly consist of developing children's musical education and learning notation literacy . General knowledge serves to form the content of concepts

Musical literacy educates students in a conscious attitude to music and its means of expression, helps to understand the original content and essence of music.

The main methodical requirement for the study of school music literacy is to use the musical-theoretical knowledge acquired during the lesson in other activities such as singing, listening to music, rhythmic accompaniment to music, accompanying children's musical instruments. it consists of being able to sing. In the course of each activity, the students will determine, at least partially, the tonality, tempo, rhythm, shape, dynamic signs, and rhythms of the works they are singing, accompanying or listening to.

In this process, musical literacy is very important. In music literacy, knowledge about musical terms, traditions, tempos, intervals, alteration signs, dynamic signs, means of expression of music, simple music forms and genres is acquired and strengthened.

In the first grade, music literacy provides the basic basic knowledge. These mainly consist of knowledge about musical sounds, their characteristics, the extension of musical notes, the writing of the 7 main sounds in the extension of musical notes, and the key symbol .

In the second grade, the theme of the year is called "types of performance" and the students of music literacy have a theoretical study on the means of expression of music - soloism, accompaniment and accompaniment, soloism and soloism, musical instruments, their types, melody, what is expressed in a melody. acquire knowledge.

In the 3rd grade, music literacy activities cover the knowledge of the following topics.

Musical means of expression. (Their application is in practical examples

- musical speech;

-choir and orchestra-theoretical and practical concepts of choir and orchestra types, structure, composition;

- structure of music, simple musical forms, refrain and refrain;

In the 4th grade, the knowledge in this direction is embodied in deeper, more complex topics;

- folk sayings and musical instruments;

- holiday and ritual songs;

- seasonal spoons;

- springtime songs;

They acquire knowledge and concepts about the order of the subjects, keys, pauses, alteration signs, liga, staccato, fermato, volta, reprise, do, sol, re, e major and yondosh, tonality .

Accompanying children's musical instruments

This activity aims to improve and develop musical performance skills of elementary school students, to arouse interest in performance, and to form emotional feelings towards musical creativity.

tasks can be included in the performance of musical instruments .

- formation of children's performance skills and abilities in school, outside of school and in free time;

interest in performing as an ensemble, as a soloist , as an accompaniment;

- to teach to distinguish musical instruments from the sound timbre, to understand the harmony in their sound;

- abilities, activation of meter, rhythm contribution - activation of musical form, timbre, harmonic, melodic hearing;

- the ideas about the elements of musical speech and means of expression of music ;

Perform dance and rhythmic movements to music

This type of activity is carried out in aesthetic education through the expressiveness of artistic-ideological music. Educational activities are of great importance. Dance, musical games and performing movements to music have a special place in the mental development and physical development of students. Performing dances and rhythmic movements in musical culture classes has a positive effect on students' musical learning, memory, and understanding of rhythm. Any type of movement is performed under the image and rhythm of a musical piece, and the musical tones associated with movement are kept in the child's memory for a long time.

Dance and rhythmic movements help to develop mobility and agility in the child, help to grow the body correctly and train the body. So, actions suitable to music are the mental sophistication of students. Along with developing abilities, it also strengthens will. For example, any movement suitable to marching music encourages students to dance by creating enthusiasm and freshness, inner feelings of dance. Children will have fun and enjoy this activity.

Based on all the considered activities, appropriate use of advanced, modern pedagogical technologies, as well as audio, video, image, voice reproduction from the multimedia tools of music education that are widely used in foreign music education. , the use of animations increases the interest of students in music lessons and ensures that they can see, hear and imagine knowledge, information and information on the given topic in reliable movements, in an artistic way. The received information helps to preserve knowledge and information in the memory for a

long time, thereby creating a basis for the quality and efficiency of education to be at a higher level.

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